

Nutritive Value and Chemical Composition of some New Hybrid Varieties of Pea (*Pisum sativum*)

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THE criteria for the selection of the best and most economic varieties of pea have generally been its yield capacity, capacity to resist insect pests and diseases and ability to grow under adverse environmental conditions. Not much consideration has been paid to the nutritive value of the pea varieties so far evolved. Data of this type are necessary for accurate nutritional research to select the best varieties for hybridization and to decide the stage of harvesting for consumption. The main objective of this work was to evaluate the difference in the nutritive value as judged from chemical composition of peas at green as well as at dry stage. The work was carried out in *rabi* season 1966-67 and the varieties taken under study were the ones recently evolved at the Regional Research Institute, Gwalior. These included some Indian and foreign varieties and their crosses.

Experimental

Five varieties, namely Greater progress, Type 19, Little Marvel, Russian-2, Duke of Albany and their intervarietal crosses, viz., T₁₉ × G.P., D.A. × G.P., Ri-2 × G.P. and T₁₉ × L.M. were selected for study. Number of varieties included in each cross was 6, 9, 7 and 13 respectively.

Chemical estimations were done for sugars, starch, vitamins (A and C), protein and minerals (Ca, Mg, P, Fe and Mn). Methods for estimating sugars

(reducing and non-reducing only in green stage) and starch were those adopted by Kanwar and Chopra¹; vitamin A by Winton and Winton²; vitamin C by Click³; protein, calcium and magnesium by Motiramani and Wankhede⁴ and iron, phosphorus, manganese by Chapman and Pratt⁵; the separation and identification of amino acids by unidimensional descending paper chromatography as described by Carter *et al.*⁶. R_F value of each amino acid was established under the conditions of the experiment. Energy values of the peas (protein and carbohydrate) were also computed (Dutcher *et al.*⁷).

Results and Discussion

Chemical composition of dry pea: Protein content of the parent varieties and their crosses ranges from (Table 1, column 3) 24.12% to 32.52% and 26.29% to 29.93% respectively. It can also be observed from the table that except Russian-2 (protein content 24.12%) all other varieties contain more than 24.50% of protein, which is the average reported value in other pea varieties (last row). The variety G.P. contains exceptionally high amount of protein (32.52%). In general, the protein contribution of the varieties is as under:

Variety G.P. > L.M. > T₁₉ > D.A. > Ri-2 and of the cross T₁₉ × G.P. > D.A. × G.P. > T₁₉ × L.M. > Ri-2 × G.P.

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF DRY PEA

Inter-varietal crosses	No. of varieties included in each cross	Protein g/100 g.	Carbo-hydrate (starch) g/100 g.	Minerals g/100 g.					Total mineral content
				Calcium	Magne-sium	Phos-phorus	Iron	Manga-nese	
T-19 × G.P.	6	29.93	50.43	0.064	0.130	0.431	0.003	0.024	0.652
D.A. × G.P.	9	28.81	50.24	0.081	0.138	0.483	0.005	0.029	0.736
Ri-2 × G.P.	7	26.29	48.70	0.085	0.140	0.432	0.004	0.028	0.689
T-19 × L.M.	13	27.65	47.10	0.065	0.135	0.475	0.003	0.025	0.703
<i>Parent varieties:</i>									
Greater Progress (G.P.)	—	32.52	55.20	0.080	0.140	0.584	0.005	0.028	0.837
Type-19 (T-19)	—	27.32	49.80	0.065	0.116	0.372	0.003	0.028	0.584
Little Marval (L.M.)	—	28.58	45.50	0.060	0.135	0.481	0.004	0.040	0.720
Russian-2 (Ri-2)	—	24.12	48.20	0.075	0.156	0.436	0.004	0.028	0.700
Duke of Albany (D.A.)	—	26.42	42.30	0.100	0.150	0.620	0.004	0.040	0.914
Average reported chemical composition of pea* (Standard).	—	24.50	61.70	0.073	0.116	0.303	0.006	0.020	0.518

* "Nutritional values" (Documenta Geigy series) Published by Suidrid Geigy Traning Ltd., Bombay, pp. 16.

TABLE 2—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF GREEN PEA

No. of varieties included in each cross	Carbohydrate g/100 g				Minerals, g/100 g					Total mineral content	Vitamin A I.U./100 g	Vitamin C g/100 g
	Starch	reducing Sugars	Non reducing	Total carbohydrate	Calcium	Magnesium	Phosphorus	Iron	Manganese			
<i>Inter-varietal crosses :</i>												
6	15.06	1.57	1.63	18.26	0.025	0.035	0.112	0.002	0.002	0.176	641.66	0.027
9	15.51	1.35	1.63	18.54	0.023	0.034	0.114	0.003	0.003	0.177	694.44	0.028
7	14.70	1.72	2.08	18.50	0.022	0.037	0.125	0.002	0.003	0.189	736.43	0.028
13	14.97	1.11	1.30	17.38	0.023	0.037	0.118	0.001	0.002	0.181	696.10	0.025
<i>Patent varieties :</i>												
—	14.85	1.12	2.23	18.20	0.023	0.043	0.138	0.004	0.004	0.212	750.00	0.028
—	13.50	1.10	1.40	16.00	0.028	0.039	0.109	0.003	0.002	0.181	580.00	0.022
—	15.30	1.31	1.65	18.26	0.020	0.037	0.128	0.002	0.002	0.189	725.00	0.022
—	16.29	2.10	2.60	20.99	0.025	0.036	0.126	0.002	0.003	0.192	875.00	0.031
—	14.99	1.32	0.64	16.95	0.026	0.033	0.146	0.003	0.002	0.210	680.00	0.028
—	—	—	—	17.00	0.022	0.030	0.122	0.002	0.004	0.180	680.00	0.026
Average reported chemical composition of Pea* (Standards)												

* "Nutritional Values" (Documenta Geigy series) Published by Suid Geigy Trading Ltd., Bombay, pp. 16.

The carbohydrate content of the varieties and their crosses ranges from 42.30% to 55.20% and 47.10% to 50.43% respectively as against 61.70%, which is the average reported value in other pea varieties. Apparently, both the varieties and the crosses are low in carbohydrate content in comparison to reported value (61.70%). However, the variety G.P. has highest amount of carbohydrate (55.20%) among the others. Total mineral content (Table 1, 10th column) of the varieties and their crosses ranges from 0.584% to 0.914% and 0.652% to 0.736% respectively as against 0.518% which is the average reported value in other pea varieties. It is clear that both the varieties and the crosses are rich in mineral content and the total mineral content of the variety D.A. > G.P. > L.M. > Ri-2 > T₁₉ and of the cross D.A. × G.P. > T₁₉ × L.M. > Ri-2 × G.P. > T₁₉ × G.P. Variety D.A. contains highest amount of total minerals (0.914%) among all the other varieties and crosses.

Chemical composition of Green Pea: Protein content of the parent varieties and their crosses (Table 2) ranges from 4.12% to 7.20% and 5.19% to 5.68% respectively as against 6.70% (last row, 3rd column), which is the average reported value in other pea varieties. It is apparent from the table that except in Greater Progress (Protein content 7.20%) the protein content of all other varieties and crosses is less than the average reported value. However, except the variety Duke of Albany (protein content 4.12%), other varieties are superior to their crosses in respect of protein content. Examining critically for carbohydrate content it can be observed that variety Russian-2 contains 2.10% reducing sugar and 2.60% non-reducing sugar and significantly high amount of total carbohydrate (20.99%, 7th column). Apparently, this would be very sweet and palatable. The cross Ri-2 × G.P. also contains reducing sugar 1.72% and non-reducing sugar 2.08%, which is significantly higher than other crosses. Hence, the variety Ri-2 and its cross Ri-2 × G.P. can be recommended for picking at green stage. Except the variety T₁₉ and D.A. all other varieties and crosses have their total carbohydrate content more than the average reported value (17.00%, last row). The total mineral content (Table 2, 13th column) of the varieties and their crosses ranges from 0.181% to 0.212% and 0.176% to 0.189% respectively as against 0.180% (last row) which is the average reported value in other pea varieties. It is also apparent that varieties are superior to their crosses in respect of total mineral content and the total mineral content of G.P. > D.A. > Ri-2 > L.M. > T₁₉. Vitamin A content (Table 2) of the varieties and their crosses ranges from 580 I.U./100 g to 875 I.U./100 g and 641 I.U./100 g to 736 I.U./100 g of pea respectively as against 680 I.U./100 g (last row), which is the average reported value in other pea varieties. Except the variety T₁₉ (Vit. A-580 I.U./100 g) and

the cross Ri-2 × G.P. (Vit. A-641.66 I.U./100 g) all other varieties and their crosses have vitamin A content greater than 680 I.U./100 g of pea, the average reported value, and except T₁₉ the varieties are superior to their crosses. Russian-2 is exceptionally rich in vitamin A. Vitamin C content (Table 2) of the varieties and their crosses is almost equal and does not deviate much from the average reported value (0.026%). The variety Ri-2 contains highest amount (0.031%) of vitamin C. Hence, it can be concluded from the results that at green stage varieties are superior to their crosses and out of these Russian-2 is the best one.

Amino acids: Paper chromatographic analysis of the hydrolysates for qualitative estimation of amino acids showed that almost all the varieties possess histidine, lysine, arginine, glycine, glutamic acid, alanine, threonine, tryptophane, phenyl alanine, valine, isoleucine and leucine at green as well as at dry stage but the amount of the former six amino acids was found to be comparatively more at green stage.

In conclusion one would recommend the variety Ri-2 for picking at green stage as it is the most nutritious as well as the sweetest and the variety G.P. and cross T-19 × G.P. for use at dry stage on account of their highest energy value and protein content.

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